

Examining the Relation between Unemployment & Inflation as represented by the Phillips Curve – A Review of Literature with Regard to the US Economy

Abstract: This paper examines the relevance of the Phillips Curve in the U.S. economy, tracing its evolution from a foundational policy tool to a framework with increasingly apparent limitations. Initially, the Phillips Curve proposed a trade-off between inflation and unemployment, guiding policy decisions in the 1960s. However, events like 1970s stagflation and the recent COVID-19 pandemic have challenged its predictive power. The paper discusses adaptations like the expectations-augmented Phillips Curve and recent research suggesting a weakening link between inflation and unemployment. It concludes that while the Phillips Curve remains historically significant, future economic models must account for technological change, globalization, and sector-specific dynamics to put forth more adaptable and effective policies.

Introduction

The imperative to understand the Phillips curve and its applicability in the US economy stems from its implication on policy frameworks. Research on the relationship between unemployment and inflation, as depicted by the Phillips Curve indicates that its linearity becomes an important indicator to policy makers. Across the different phases of the business cycle, a linear Phillips curve is suggestive of a symmetric monetary policy response. (Kumar & Orrenius, 2016). However, with a nonlinear Phillips curve—where inflation escalates rapidly as the unemployment rate falls below the natural rate—preemptive action may be necessary to curb inflation as the economy approaches its potential output. Conversely, if the Phillips curve is relatively flat, monetary policy should prioritize responding to shifts in unemployment over inflation adjustments. (Laseen and Sanjani, 2016)

A. Importance of Inflation & Unemployment for an Economy

Understanding the dynamics of unemployment and inflation is crucial for both economists and policymakers due to their high impact on economic stability, societal well-being, and the development of effective policy measures.

High unemployment rates lead to lost income, reduced consumer spending, and increased government expenditure on welfare benefits, which can strain public finances and impact economic growth. Socially, unemployment can lead to increased poverty, mental health issues, and a decline in skills among workers, which can further cause long-term unemployment. This is supported by studies such as Blanchard and Katz (1997), which highlight the social costs associated with prolonged unemployment, including reduced quality of life and heightened social tensions.

High inflation reduces consumer purchasing power, diminishes savings, and creates uncertainty in the economy from firms and consumers. Persistent inflation can destabilize economies by leading to a loss of confidence in currency which can affect the level the levels of net current trade balance as import prices increase while export prices decrease. According to Gordon (1997), understanding the relationship between inflation and unemployment is essential for setting

appropriate monetary policies, such as inflation targeting, which aims to maintain price stability through manipulating interest rates, while promoting economic growth.

Recent events, such as the Great Recession (Dec 2007-June 2009) and the COVID-19 pandemic, have further highlighted the importance of studying unemployment and inflation. These crises revealed how quickly economic shocks can disrupt the balance between unemployment and inflation, resulting in widespread economic and social issues. For example, the pandemic-induced lockdowns led to sharp spikes in unemployment and significant disruptions to inflation, challenging traditional economic models and necessitating innovative policy responses to stabilize the economy (Federal Reserve Bank of Atlanta, 2021).

By studying unemployment and inflation, economists can better understand the underlying mechanisms driving economic cycles and develop policies that promote sustainable economic growth.

B. The Phillips Curve and its Limitations

The Phillips curve was first introduced by A.W. Phillips in 1958, derived from when he analyzed data on unemployment and wage inflation in the UK from 1861 to 1957. He observed a 'consistent, inverse relationship'¹ between the rate of unemployment and the rate of wage inflation. During periods of low unemployment wages seemed to increase rapidly due to increase demand for labor. During periods of high unemployment, wages did not grow and in some cases, growth was negative. He presented his findings into a single graph depicting the inverse relation between inflation and unemployment.

The simplicity of the Phillips Curve finds drew attention from many economists and policy makers and the curve became a key tool in the 1960's to create economic policy where governments could reduce unemployment and expect high inflation rates. This led to countries opting for demand side policies where fiscal and monetary policies were designed to change aggregate demand to reduce inflation that was a byproduct of reduced employment.

The belief behind the Phillips Curve significantly reduced after the 1970s during a period of stagflation, which is a scenario characterized by simultaneous high inflation and high unemployment. The traditional Phillips Curve could not explain this as the expected inverse relationship between inflation and unemployment broke down. This time period exposed the limitations of the curve, leading to skepticism regarding its reliability.

C. The Expectation Augmented Phillips Curve

Phelps (1967,1968) and Friedman (1968) were instrumental in trying to solve the theoretical gaps exposed by stagflation. Their main idea was that the original Phillips Curve failed to account for inflation expectations. The introduction of adaptive and rational expectations provided a pivotal shift in understanding, emphasizing that inflationary expectations could erode the trade-off's

¹ Hoover, K.D., *The Genesis of Samuelson and Solow's Price-Inflation Phillips Curve, Research*. Available at: <https://public.econ.duke.edu/~kdh9/Source%20Materials/Research/SamuelsonSolowHER.pdf> (Accessed: 28 August 2024).

stability, thus necessitating a reevaluation of policy frameworks. Phelps (1967,1968) and Friedman (1968) accounted for the role of anticipated inflation, suggesting that workers and firms adjust their expectations based on past experiences, thereby influencing the actual inflation-unemployment relationship.

The Friedman-Phelps expectations-augmented model posits that the short-term trade-off between inflation and unemployment can only be exploited if inflation expectations are static. Once economic agents anticipate changes in inflation, the curve becomes vertical in the long run, implying no trade-off between inflation and unemployment. This concept has influenced modern monetary policy, emphasizing the importance of managing inflation expectations to achieve economic stability.

After the rise of the expectations-augmented Phillips Curve, Robert Gordon(1997) further developed these ideas in the late 1970s and 1980s by integrating the role of supply side shocks (for example oil prices increase) and demand side shocks (such as contractionary and expansionary monetary policy) into the augmented Phillips Curve framework. This increased the flexibility of the curve and more importantly considered how external factors could change inflation, independent of unemployment.

The Great Recession (Rich, 2013) and the unprecedented economic impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic have prompted renewed interest in examining the curve's applicability in modern economic contexts. Evidence suggests that the Phillips Curve may have flattened further in recent decades. This is because inflation has shown less sensitivity to the changes in unemployment. Studies like those by Blanchard (2016) argue that while the Phillips Curve relationship still exists, it has become more complex and less predictable, necessitating ongoing adaptation in economic theory and policy. Empirical studies have explored how changes in the global economy, technological advancements, and shifts in market structures affect the Phillips curve dynamics, providing nuanced insights into its behavior under various economic conditions.

This paper aims to review the existing literature to determine the extent to which the Phillips curve represents the relationship between unemployment and inflation accurately for the US economy. It attempts to comprehensively study the research on limitations of the traditional Phillips Curve in respect of the US economy, and the adaptations made to justify the Phillips Curve in view of the changing relationship between unemployment and inflation in the US economy.

Review and Analysis of Empirical Evidence in the US Economy

Several empirical studies have been used to evaluate the accuracy of the Phillips curve in the US economy. This is done through employing econometric models that account for both the short run and long run relationships between unemployment and inflation. Appendix A summarizes the major events in the US economy from 1955-2024, and their impact on inflation and unemployment in a bid to assess the applicability of the traditional Phillips Curve.

The early 1960s was a time period when significant research was done on testing the application of the Phillips curve. Samuelson and Solow (1960) built on the work of A.W. Phillips working with US data from the late 1950s and early 1960s, they found the inverse relationship between inflation

and unemployment. According to their calculations the US could reduce unemployment from 6% to 4% but at the cost of inflation rising from 1.5% to around 4%. This is closely aligned with the historical data where unemployment averaged 5.5% between 1955 and 1960 while inflation remained below 2% during the same period. This led to the Phillips curve being a key tool for policymakers, leading to the widespread adoption of fiscal and monetary policy aimed at adjusting the economy.

Figure 1: Inflation and Unemployment, 1955–1996 (King, 2008)²

However, as the decade progressed inflation started to increase. By 1965 the unemployment fell to 4.5% and inflation rose to 1.6% highlighting a steeper trade off between the relationship. Policy makers supported the success of the Phillips Curve frame and continued to push for lower unemployment by increasing aggregate demand. This led to inflation increasing and reaching to 3% by 1967 with unemployment falling to 3.8%

The 1970s was one of the most challenging period; the US economy experienced stagflation a combination of high inflation and high unemployment which contradicts the inverse relationship of the Phillips Curve. In 1971, US unemployment hovered around 6%, while inflation was still relatively low at 3.4%. However the oil price shocks of 1973 and 1974 caused for inflation to surge to 11% and unemployment also rose to 8.5% by 1975. This period of high inflation and high unemployment as previously mentioned contradicted the traditional Phillips Curve. The external shocks to the supply side of the economy through oil prices led to cost push inflation which was not taken into account by the demand side models of the Phillips Curve.

² King, R. G. (2008). *The Phillips Curve and U.S. Macroeconomic Policy: Snapshots, 1958–1996*. Federal Reserve Bank of Richmond.

In the late 1980s, the concept of Non-Accelerating Inflation rate of unemployment (NAIRU) gained significant prominence as an interpretation of the Phillips Curve. Empirical analysis by Gordon (1997) showed that the Phillips Curve remained valid but the slope flattened in the 1990s. His data analysis from 1980 to 1995 shows that unemployment would need to fall below around 5.5% which was the estimated NAIRU at the time to cause accelerating inflation. However, due to inflation expectations the trade off between inflation and unemployment became weaker.

By 1995 inflation was stable at 2.5% on the other hand unemployment had fallen to 5.6%, just above the estimated NAIRU. (refer Fig 1 & 2). This time period saw the US economy benefit from both low inflation and low unemployment. Economists at the time attributed this to structural changes in the economy such as increase global competition, technological advancements and improved monetary policy.

Figure 2: Annual Unemployment Rate in the US from 1990-2023 (SOURCE: Statista)

Figure 3: Annual Inflation Rate in the US from 1990-2023 (SOURCE: Statista)

A study by Haug and King (2011) using data from 1952-2010 concluded that long-run empirical evidence for the US economy supported a positive correlation between inflation and unemployment. Their analysis showed that inflation leads unemployment by 3 to 3.5 years in cycles lasting between 8 and 50 years. These findings strongly contradict the short run negative correlation presented by the traditional Phillips curve. According to Sayeed, Islam, Yasmin (2019), over the period 2008Q1-2017Q4., the long run Phillips curve for the US economy has become flatter. Their study supports the view that post the crisis, the US economy has been faced a complex relation between inflation and unemployment. Their study, accompanied by others, challenge conventional monetary policy, highlighting the necessity of nuanced policy approaches that consider the potential long-run trade-offs in achieving both low inflation and low unemployment simultaneously.

A study by Bergholt, Furlanetto and Vaccaro-Grange (2023) aimed at explaining the stability in inflation post mid-1990s, and more significantly during the Great Recession. They looked at three main explanations of the disconnection between inflation and economic activity. First, the "slope hypothesis", which posits a flattened Phillips curve due to factors like globalization and increased market concentration. Second, the "policy hypothesis", suggesting that the Federal Reserve's stricter inflation control had minimized demand-driven inflation changes, and third, the "shock hypothesis" which attributed inflation's stability to the changing nature of economic shocks, such as the dominance of supply shocks (e.g., oil shocks) after the Great Recession.

Occhino (2019) too found a weaker correlation between economic activity and inflation in the US economy over this period. According to him, this change could result from two main factors: either a structural shift in the economy, like increased price flexibility, or an altered monetary policy response by the Federal Reserve. Using a New Keynesian economic model, he explored these possibilities and demonstrated that each scenario has different implications for monetary policy and its impact on household welfare.

The Federal Reserve Bank of Atlanta (2021) examined how the Phillips Curve behaved during the COVID-19 pandemic, mainly using regional and national US economy data. The US experienced record high unemployment from 3.5% in February 2020 to 14.8% in April 2020. This level of unemployment has not been seen since the Great Depression. Usually a large increase in unemployment would be followed by significant deflation according to the original Phillips Curve. However, the Personal Consumption Expenditures (PCE) index, reduced modestly from 1.8% in 2019 to 1.4% in 2020. This small decline was mainly affected by supply chain disruptions and expansionary fiscal policy interventions such as expanded unemployment benefits which kept consumer demand afloat despite high unemployment rates.

Their data analysis revealed that in regions in which the pandemic affected unemployment rates to extremely high levels, the Phillips Curve relationship was almost flat with almost no correlation between changes in unemployment and inflation. For example in New York and California where unemployment peaked above 16% in 2020, inflation data showed minimal sensitivity to labor market conditions.

The Federal Reserve study (2021) showed that the labor market slack historically showed 10-15% inflation variability. During the pandemic this figure fell to less than 5% with government spending and disrupted supply chains contributing a much larger share of inflation dynamics. This overall

suggested that significant economic shocks such as the COVID-19 pandemic may cause the Phillips Curve framework to become less reliable in predicting inflationary outcomes.

Conclusion

It is essential to recognize that the Phillips Curve has played a fundamental role in illustrating the historical trade-off between unemployment and inflation. However, as evidenced by this review, shifts in technology, globalization, and sector-specific dynamics challenge its current relevance. The evolution of labor markets, driven by automation and artificial intelligence, presents new complexities as traditional relationships between unemployment and inflation may further weaken or become unpredictable. These advancements can reshape labor markets through replacing traditional jobs and shift labor demand towards highly skilled sectors the relationship between unemployment and inflation may become even more disconnected. Future search should focus on developing models that are adjusted for these labor market disruptions as many sectors can experience persistent unemployment in the future. Therefore, the Phillips Curve may no longer serve as a singular framework for guiding policy.

In terms of policy construction, managing inflation expectation will still remain an important tool. With flattening of the Phillips Curve future monetary policies will have to move beyond traditional economic frameworks. Policy makers should use dynamic approaches that consider external factors that the traditional Phillips Curve does not consider.

Additionally, the differences between sectors of the economy such as housing, healthcare and technology also need to be considered. The relationship between inflation and unemployment does not work the same way in every industry. For example, during the Great Recession, the housing market experienced inflation due to other factors like interest rates, not just unemployment. Future economic models should focus more on how each sector behaves differently, instead of treating the economy as one single unit. This would help policymakers create better, more targeted solutions that address the needs of specific industries, making the economy more stable.

In light of this, it is clear that policymakers and economists must move beyond traditional frameworks like the Phillips Curve. By developing adaptive models that incorporate external and sector-specific factors, economic policy can be better positioned to achieve sustainable growth and macroeconomic stability in a rapidly changing economic landscape. Thus, while the Phillips Curve has historical significance, future economic strategies should embrace more dynamic and multifaceted approaches to remain effective in addressing the complexities of modern economies.

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Appendix A: Evolving Dynamics of the Phillips Curve Relationship in the US Economy

[Adapted in part from King(2008)]

Period	Significant Events in U.S. Economy	Unemployment and Inflation Trends	Phillips Curve Relationship
1955–1961	Initial Phillips curve studies conducted amid two recessions (Aug 1957–Apr 1958, Apr 1960–Feb 1961).	Unemployment increased as Inflation dropped.	Suggested inverse relationship, showing initial Phillips curve stability .
1962–1968	Economic policies focused on reducing unemployment.	Unemployment decreased significantly; inflation stable initially, then increased toward 1968.	Indicated Phillips curve trade-off : lower unemployment led to rising inflation.
1969–1979	Departure from the gold standard, energy crises, and wage/price controls.	Both unemployment and inflation increased during recessions in 1969–1970 and 1973–1975.	Weakened Phillips curve validity , as both unemployment and inflation rose simultaneously (stagflation).
1980–1985	Period of high-interest rates aimed at controlling inflation ("Volcker shock").	Inflation decreased substantially, but unemployment remained high.	Phillips curve relationship partially restored , as policies focused on inflation reduction despite unemployment consequences.
1986–1996	Phillips curve integrated into new monetary policy models post-Volcker era.	Stabilized inflation with moderate, stable unemployment.	Phillips curve redefined in policy models, reflecting a weaker trade-off due to policy adjustments.
1997–2007	Stable growth in a low-inflation environment; expansion of global trade and technology boom.	Low and stable inflation with declining unemployment.	Flattened Phillips curve , as economic growth did not lead to significant inflation increases.
2008–2009	Global Financial Crisis and Great Recession. Federal Reserve employed quantitative easing (QE) and near-zero interest rates.	Sharp rise in unemployment, but inflation remained relatively low.	Phillips curve relationship weakened , with high unemployment but stable inflation.
2010–2019	Long recovery period with continued QE; low unemployment and low inflation.	Unemployment gradually declined to historic lows, but inflation remained below 2%.	Phillips curve further flattened , suggesting a weaker link between low unemployment and rising inflation.
2020–2021	COVID-19 pandemic recession, rapid fiscal and	Initial spike in unemployment;	Temporary breakdown of Phillips curve as

	monetary stimulus. Disruptions in global supply chains and labor market shifts.	inflation remained low, then surged in 2021 as economy reopened.	pandemic-related factors led to both high unemployment and eventual inflation spike.
2022–2024	Post-pandemic recovery with Federal Reserve's shift to tightening policies to control inflation ("inflation surge"). Persistent supply chain issues, energy price volatility, and labor market adjustments.	Declining unemployment but elevated inflation due to supply constraints; interest rate hikes to curb inflation.	Phillips curve partially restored as high inflation prompted aggressive rate hikes despite low unemployment. <i>Supply-side factors influenced inflation beyond traditional Phillips curve dynamics.</i>